

Diallel analysis of Al toxicity tolerance in rice

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We studied the genetics of Al toxicity tolerance using a full diallel set of crosses among seven parents with differing degrees of response to Al toxicity. The seven varieties were Moroberekan, IRAT104, and Azucena (tolerant); IR29 and IR43 (moderately tolerant); and IR45 and IR1552 (susceptible).

Relative root length of 14-d-old seedlings, determined by growing seedlings in a normal nutrient solution and nutrient solution with 30 ppm Al, was used to characterize the tolerance of test materials. The experiment was conducted in a glasshouse at the IRRI Phytotron with 29/21 °C day/night temperature and 70% relative humidity. The experimental units consisted of 49 entries (7 × 7 diallel) in randomized complete block design with four replications. Eight seedlings were sampled for each entry in a replication.

Analysis of variance among parents, hybrids, and reciprocals showed highly significant differences among parents and hybrids. Differences between parents and hybrids were not significant. Analysis of variance of the diallels revealed homogeneity of error variance, directional dominance, symmetrical distribution of genes among parents, and that no parent had more dominant genes than did the others.

Covariance-variance graphic analysis showed the adequacy of a simple additive-

Estimates of genetic parameters for relative root length (Al toxicity tolerance) in 7 × 7 diallel cross. IRRI, 1995.

Genetic parameter		Estimate ± SE	
(D) Additive effects		0.0167	± 0.0005 ^a
(H) Dominance effects			
	H1 (due to dominant gene)	0.0041	± 0.0015*
	H2 (due to positive and negative genes)	0.0034	± 0.0013*
	h ² (due to heterozygous loci)	-0.0002	± 0.0009
(F) Gene distribution		0.0028	± 0.0015
(E) Environmental effects		0.0008	± 0.0002*
Proportional values			
(H1/D) ^{1/2}	Mean degree of dominance	0.4954	
(H2/4H1)	Proportion of genes with + or - effects on parents	0.2082	
(KD/KR) ^b	Proportion of dominant and recessive genes in the parents	1.4001	
r ^c	Correlation between (Wr+Vr) and Yr	0.6618	
r ²	Prediction for measurement of completely dominant and recessive parents	0.4380	
(h ² /H2)	Number of gene groups that control tolerance and inhibit dominance	-0.0654	
(h _{ns})	Heritability (narrow sense)	0.8177	
(h _{bs})	Heritability (broad sense)	0.9106	

^a * = significant at P<0.05. ^b KD/KR = [(4DH₁)^{1/2} + FJ]/[(4DH₁)^{1/2} - FJ]. ^c r = correlation between the sum of covariance of an array with nonrecurring parents and variance of an array (Wr + Vr) and parental means (Yr).

dominance model and partial dominance of the trait. It also showed the presence of dominant genes in tolerant varieties and recessive genes in susceptible varieties. Moderately tolerant to tolerant varieties IR43, Azucena, IRAT104, and Moroberekan appeared to contain similar genes for tolerance. Susceptible IR45 possessed most of the recessive genes for tolerance, followed by IR29 and IR1552.

Genetic components of variation and proportional values were estimated (see table). The observed variations were due to additive and dominance effects of genes and the environmental effects. Average degree of dominance was within the range of incomplete dominance. The proportion of dominant and recessive genes in the

parents indicated an excess of dominant genes. Genes with desirable effects (tolerance) were dominant over those with undesirable effects (susceptibility). Only one group of genes with dominance was found to be involved in governing Al toxicity tolerance in rice.

The high narrow-sense heritability (0.82) and the small difference between narrow-sense and broad-sense heritability (0.91) indicated the predominance of additive gene action. Results indicated that in breeding populations, selection for Al toxicity tolerance could be carried out in the early generations. Selection efficiency could be enhanced if done under controlled conditions to reduce environmental effects. ■

Breeding methods

Maintainers and restorers for cytoplasmic male sterile line IR66707 A

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Since its release in India during 1992, IR64 has become very popular in the irrigated areas of Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh,

Orissa, West Bengal, and Maharashtra. It has high yield, wide adaptability, good plant type, long slender grain, intermediate amylose content, and resistance to major insect pests and diseases.

IRRI scientists developed cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line IR66707A from IR64 by using *Oryza perennis* as a cytoplasmic source. Their intention was to use this CMS line to develop high-yielding, good quality hybrid rice. However, hybrids could

not be developed without effective restorers.

During 1992-93, we made 50 test crosses with IR66707 A using high-yielding varieties adapted to irrigated and rainfed lowland conditions. We found 42 of the varieties to be effective maintainers; one a weak maintainer; five partial restorers; and two, IR21820-38-2 and Mahsuri, to be effective restorers for IR66707 A (Table 1). Unlike in the CMS-wild abortive system,